

REMOTE CONTROLLED LAKE GARBAGE REMOVER

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Abstract – we know that villages present in all states of India are joint with small & big lake and maximum villages does not use the water of lake for farming, drinking and daily uses due to large amount of garbage present in the lake water, by taking this into consideration our main motive is to clean the garbage in lake water for that we are making efficient lake garbage collector by using remote controlled air propeller boat. The proposed machine is intended for physically removing garbage floating on the water bodies. This machine is expected to save considerable manpower, expenditure and mainly to avoid the infestation. This project is aimed at development of an experimental prototype for demonstration of basic functionality.

Key Words: Air propeller boat, trash collector, with remote control.

INTRODUCTION

For the simple reason that all known forms of life on Earth rely on water in some way. Despite having access to an abundance of water, water pollution remains a major concern for many countries. Eighty percent of India's water sources are polluted, according to "Wateraid," an organisation working to achieve satisfaction in cleanliness and water sterilisation. Garbage, weeds, plastic, sewage, effluents, and hazardous items from companies are being skimmed from water bodies, making them dirtier. In agricultural countries, the urgent problem of water pollution caused by skimming waste requires immediate attention.

It is time-consuming, labor-intensive, and expensive to clean water lakes by hand. Workers' safety is a major concern when it comes to manual cleaning. In addition to wounds produced by work-related accidents, health consequences can include musculoskeletal, digestive, and vector-borne diseases. This calls for plans to automate the present system for

cleaning the surface of waterways, simply using little tools that the general public may use.

1. THE SITUATION

trash skimmer boats are one method for gathering and eliminating riverine or marine trash. When floating debris poses a navigational risk, devices like this might be deployed. Collecting what is known as "sea shore litter" requires both manual sorting and the use of focused sea coast cleaning machinery. Skimmer boats are an expensive way to remove plastic, and they need constant maintenance and more workers to finish the cycle. The current method of manual expulsion in lakes and coastal areas is ineffective since it requires regular removal of trash to prevent it from reaching the ocean. The removal of plastic waste from the water is still in its early phases. But other projects have already started, such Kaisei and New Horizon, which used net-equipped boats to collect trash for scientific study. Crafted from aluminium, it is designed for effortless operation and ease of ownership. The boat has an hourly capacity to channel a water surface of 92 by 92 metres. You may adjust the channel structure to collect trash of different sizes. Marine cleaners come in both freshwater and saltwater varieties, and they all use the same articulated vertical wing capture system that sends debris to the front loader. You can easily retrieve both large and little goods, and cross spikes will prevent you from moving backwards. All skimming, load handling, and impetus capabilities are handled by a comprehensive hydraulic system that the administrator may manage at varied speeds. A clamor-sealed, lockable motor room houses an air-cooled diesel hydraulic power unit. A framework for motor control inspection, featuring warning lights, a tachometer, an hour metre, and water-driven controls with pressure measurement; the foundation also includes a seat and support for the administrator. Transport network

System supported by UHMD plastic rails and appropriate flooring, constructed of uncompromising stainless steel. The front conveyor of the verbalised skimmer wings has changeable depth settings and belts mounted spikes. A capacity conveyor that may be adjusted for height and has a hydraulic system for arranging loads. The existing system makes use of massive hardware in the image. Bring or force weeds to the beach. One major drawback of the type is that it requires skilled staff to run and has a high cost for the equipment. This equipment is too expensive for farmers. The machine is enormous. Transporting it requires

a large truck. There is an enormous demand for a resource like fuels.

- to run the machines for only few hours.

Fig. 1 Existing System

1. OBJECTIVES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

- To clean the garbage present in small lakes.
- To minimise the use of fuel operated garbage collector.
- To tackle the problems regarding wastage, food material, plastics present in the lake.
- To minimize the human efforts required to clean the lakes.
- To clean the polluted water due to which save the aquatic animal

A. HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS:

- Aurdino uno micro controller
- Bluetooth module
- Relay module
- Dc motors
- Propellers
- Rechargeable battery
- Solar panel
- PVC pipes and iron mesh

B. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS:

- Arduino IDE
- Embedded c-language

C. BLOCK DIAGRAM:

Fig. 2 Block diagram of proposed system

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of proposed system

D. COMPONENT DESCRIPTION:

Arduino UNO: Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board dependent on the ATmega328P (datasheet). It has 14 advanced information/yield pins (of which 6 are frequently utilized as PWM yields), 6 simple data sources, 16 MHz quartz, a USB association, an impact jack, an ICSP header and a reset button.

Fig. 4 Arduino UNO

Bluetooth Module: Any Bluetooth-enabled device, including computers, mobile phones, and more, may be communicated with by this module. The tiny regulator's sequential UART port is how it communicates with the microcontroller. Bluetooth is a 2.4 GHz distant correspondences standard that is well-suited to the development of regional organisations because of its client-server architecture. When it comes to low-force devices, Bluetooth is a crucial component. A standard feature or determination, Bluetooth is available in all Smartphone PCs. Simple and designed for easy distant sequential association setup, the HC-05 module (shown in Figure-1) is a Bluetooth SPP (Serial Port Protocol) module. A fully approved Bluetooth V2.0+EDR (3 Mbps) modulation module with a 2.4 GHz radio handset and baseband is available in this sequential port Bluetooth device. The HC-05 module can be controlled from 3.0 to 4.2 V and operates on 3.0 V low force activity. A programmable baud rate UART interface, an edge connection, and receiving equipment are all built in. Data bits: 8, Stop bit: 1, and default Baud rate: 38400 for the HC-05 module. The following baud rates are supported: 9600, 19200, 38400, 57600, 115200, 230400, and 460800; there is no equality.

Fig. 5 Bluetooth module

Relay module: A relay is an electrically worked switch that can be turned on or off, releasing the flow through or not, and can be controlled with low voltages; similar to the 5V gave by the Arduino pins. This transfer module has two channels (those blue 3D squares). There are different models with one, four and eight channels. This module should be controlled with 5V, which is proper to use with an Arduino.

Fig. 6 Two channel relay module

DC Motor: D.C. motor is controlled by DC voltages and moves in forward, backward, left and right, direction according to the polarity of voltage applied. Generally all mechanical development which robot performs is cultivated by an electric engine. Electric machines are methods for changing over energy into mechanical energy. Electric engine is utilized to control gadgets. An illustration of little engine applications, for example, engines utilized in autos, robot, hand power devices and food blenders.

Fig. 7 DC Motor

PROPELLER: A **propeller** is a device with a rotating hub and radiating blades that are set at a pitch to form a helical spiral, that, when rotated, performs an action which is similar to Archimedes' screw. It transforms rotational power into linear thrust by acting upon a working fluid, such as water or air.

Fig. 8 Propeller

Rechargeable battery: Now days we are utilizing Rechargeable batteries for any contraption why since, in such a case that we utilize ordinary batteries for any framework we need to supplant the batteries at whatever point it's necessary which isn't a favorable position. Where we come to Rechargeable batteries where it isn't important to change the batteries rather than that we are going charge the battery again at whatever points it is released. So for our proposed arrangement we are utilizing "12V" Rechargeable battery.

Fig. 9 Rechargeable battery

Solar panel: A PV module is an assembly of photo-voltaic cells mounted in a framework for installation. Photovoltaic cells use daylight as a wellspring of energy and create direct flow power. An assortment of PV modules is known as a PV Panel, and an arrangement of Panels is an Array. Varieties of a photovoltaic framework supply sunlight based power to electrical hardware.

Fig. 10 DC Motor

PVC Pipes and IRON Mesh: Why we are using PVC pipes means it has more advantages and flexibility than the plastic pipes. So the benefits of these pipes are shown below.

Benefits of PVC pipes:

- PVC Pipe is a result of present day innovation that offers dependable and strong support of an assortment of clients including temporary workers, engineers, or moperators, ventures, utilities, and water system locale. Various execution points of interest imply PVC Pipes presently supplant numerous customary materials.

- Lightweight: PVC pipes offer a tremendous weight advantage over alternative piping materials. The comparatively low weight of PVC piping means that installers are less likely to get injured, and while it may take a team of workers or mechanical hoists to carry a large section of metal pipe, PVC Pipe is so light that a single person could easily move a long piece.
- Flexibility: PVC Pipe's resistance to fracture is an extremely important performance advantage. While PVC Pipes are made from rigid PVC compound, the PVC Pipe itself has the ability to yield under loading without fracturing. PVC Pipes can successfully be used where the surface will be subject to external loading such as road traffic.

2. WORKING

DC motors are used to provide air propulsion. The vehicle's propulsion is powered using re-chargeable battery. Speed Controller mechanism using PWM signals is used to control the speed of the dc motors. The electronic hardware modules for control and communications are mounted centrally on top of the frame structure. Iron mesh which is fitted inside the pipes is used for garbage collection. A convenient mobile user interface is used for carrying out communications using HC-05 Bluetooth module.

3. RESULTS

Figure showing the boat frame, motors, air propellers and electronic box.

Fig. 11 Boat Model

Figure showing electronics used for movement (relay module, Bluetooth module, battery, arduino uno)

Fig. 12 Electronic hardware

Figure showing the trash collection while running on water body.

Fig. 13 garbage collection on the water bodies

4. CONCLUSION

The "REMOTE CONTROLLED LAKE GARBAGE REMOVER" project aspires to be a cost-effective and useful tool for cleaning rivers and ponds. Its design, estimated cost, and availability make it both inexpensive and socially beneficial.

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